

Publication Policy of the National Research Data Infrastructure for Personal Health Data (NFDI4Health)

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DOI: 10.4126/FRL01-006484167

Version: V2_1

Release date: 21.02.2025

1. Introduction

One goal of the NFDI4Health¹ at whole is to improve the management of research data from health-related studies and use cases in epidemiology, public health and clinical research. The project team aims to assist the research community in making relevant German studies easier to find and to improve data sharing in the sense of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles². To achieve this goal, a central infrastructure component, the **Health Study Hub**³ has been established by NFDI4Health and the NFDI4Health Task Force COVID-19. The Health Study Hub serves as a central inventory of German epidemiological, clinical and public health studies, as well as structured health data from registers and administrative health databases. It facilitates the publication of and search for health research data, including metadata.

¹ About NFDI4Health, <https://www.nfdi4health.de/en/>

² FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

³ Health Study Hub, <https://health-study-hub.de/>

This **Publication Policy** describes the requirements for the publication of research data from health-related studies in the Health Study Hub. Researchers or research groups wanting to make their studies findable and corresponding research data FAIR should fulfil these requirements. Table 1 shows the steps needed for publication in the Health Study Hub depending on the type of research data (i.e. “study description” or “study documents”) according to the Publication Policy. The text of the Publication Policy can be found in Section 2 of this document.

Table 1 Publication steps

1. Define the types of resources to be published	Study / Registry description	Study documents
2. Fill in the metadata schema to describe resources and to make them findable	✓	✓
3. Prepare study documents in re-usable formats	✗	✓
4. Define a (open) license to clarify copyright issues	✗	✓
5. Have a DOI assigned by the NFDI4Health to ensure persistent findability	✓	✓
6. Have the metadata reviewed by the NFDI4Health team	✓	✓
7. Contact the NFDI4Health team in case of any questions	✓	✓
8. Publish resources on the Health Study Hub	✓	✓

Table 1. Steps to publish research data in the Health Study Hub, depending on their type in accordance with the Publication Policy of the NFDI4Health, *Explanation:* “✓”: Requirement applies; “✗”: Requirement does not apply / cannot be fulfilled

2. NFDI4 Health Publication Policy

One of the purposes of the Health Study Hub is to make data collected in health-related studies FAIR. The first step towards this is the publication of comprehensive information about the context and accessibility of the data (study metadata to describe the study). In addition, study documents contain further detailed information needed for the correct interpretation of the collected data and should therefore be published as well. Accordingly, two main types of research data or resources can be found in the Health Study Hub.

2.1. Resource types

In the Health Study Hub, two main types of resources can be published:

- a. **Study / Registry descriptions** which comprise comprehensive information (metadata) about interventional or non-interventional (sub-)studies or about registries, respectively, from clinical, epidemiological or public health sector.
- b. **Study documents** which provide information about studies or research-related content such as the design, conduct or instruments used. Study documents are made available to the users of the Health Study Hub for download. Below, the most common types of study documents are listed:
 - Study protocol (study plan, study proposal)
 - Dataset
 - Participant/Patient information sheet
 - Participant tasks
 - Informed consent form (template)
 - Manual of operations/standard operating procedures (SOPs)
 - Data management plan
 - Statistical analysis plan

Further, special types of study document that can be published in the Study Hub is related to the way data is collected such as:

- Questionnaire/Case report form (CRF)
- Data dictionary (data catalogue)
- Code book
- Interview schema and themes
- Observation guide
- Discussion guide
- Biobank
- Secondary data source
- Other types of documents used for data collection

Participant/patient individual data collected in studies are **not considered** a resource type and will not be published in the Health Study Hub. However, information on the availability of the collected data must be provided as part of a study description.

NFDI4Health is currently working on an access portal extending the German Portal for Medical Research Data (FDPG, <https://forschen-fuer-gesundheit.de>) that will grant access to participant/patient individual data to interested researchers upon request. More information on the single study documents and the file formats they can be submitted in can be found in section 2.6 “Study documents and file formats” of this document.

2.2. Metadata schema

To enable a standardised collection of metadata, i.e. information describing the resources (Section 2.1 lists all eligible resource types), the NFDI4Health **metadata schema**^{4,5} needs to be filled in, either via user interface or via API. The metadata fields are divided into mandatory and recommended ones. Although only some fields are mandatory, users are encouraged to provide as much information as possible to improve the findability of resources. In addition to bibliographic information such as title and description of a resource, the persons and organisations that are involved in the development of a resource can also be included. The study results published in journal articles or other text publications can also be linked.

⁴ NFDI4Health Metadata schema V3_3, <https://repository.publisso.de/resource/fr!%3A6472531>

⁵ NFDI4Health Metadata schema V3_3 in ART-DECOR, <https://art-decor.org/ad/#/nfdhtfcov19-/project/publication>

For studies, registries and secondary data sources, additional information should be provided about their design, accessibility of the data collected, and – if applicable – further information on study content, e.g. dietary assessments, chronic diseases or record linkage.

The research data publication team will be happy to provide further information or assist in the completion of the metadata form: helpdesk@nfdi4health.de.

2.3 Language

The metadata should be provided in English, but German is also accepted.

The language of the resources themselves, i.e. the language in which a study is conducted or the language in which a submitted study document is written, is not limited to English and German.

2.4 Licensing

2.4.1 Licensing of metadata

Metadata, e.g. the descriptions of studies or study documents, are not subject to copyright and, therefore, do not need to be licensed and can be freely used after publication.

2.4.2 Licensing of study documents

Study documents are copyrighted works. To foster reusability of the published documents – which is an important point of the FAIR data principles – authors of study documents may allow third parties to use them (i.e. make a copy, redistribute, edit, post online). Open standard licenses have been developed to simplify the distribution of a work⁶. The best known and most widely used standard licenses are the Creative Commons [licenses](#) (CC licenses).

CC licenses are made up of different modules (license modules) which can be combined with each other to compile an individual license according to requirements and to grant the corresponding use. By specifying the license modules, clear, unambiguous and above all, legally clean regulations on how

⁶ Further information on licensing, including explanations of license modules and the selection of a suitable license, can be found in the flyer "Publish study documents and survey instruments quickly and easily", [NFDI4Health Task Force COVID-19 flyer Publish study documents and survey instruments quickly and easily DINlang V2 1.pdf](#)

the materials can be handled further by third parties are ensured.

Some combinations of CC license modules largely restrict the re-use of resources which is why NFDI4Health strongly recommends determining a less restrictive license for works uploaded to the Health Study Hub. Below is a list of suggested licenses:

- CC BY 4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License)
- CC BY-NC 4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International Public License)
- CC BY-SA 4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International Public License)
- CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International Public License)

Although CC licenses are preferred, other license models are also possible.

2.4.2.1 Labelling study documents with a license

For the terms and conditions of the selected license to take effect, the work in questions must be properly marked. This is often achieved by adding a statement that the material is licensed under the chosen CC license and attaching the link to the CC webpage where the standard text of the license agreement can be found. As study documents are available for download and, therefore, can be used offline, a simple indication of the license on an individual webpage of the resource in the Health Study Hub is not sufficient: The license statement and the link to the license text should be inserted directly in the files. For example, if a study document is to be licensed under the CC BY 4.0 license, the following text should be included:

“This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0). To view a copy of the license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>.”

The Creative Commons help page⁷ provides further important information on marking works with a CC license. The NFDI4Health will gladly license documents uploaded in the Health Study Hub. Researchers interested in publishing their study documents with a CC license, can contact helpdesk@nfdi4health.de.

2.4.2.2 Important notes

When selecting a CC license, some important notes should be taken into account:

⁷ About Creative Commons licenses, <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses/>

CC licenses are irrevocable: A later withdrawal of the rights granted by a CC license is not possible. Only works free of third-party rights can be licensed: Only the copyright holder or someone with expressed permission from the copyright holder can apply a CC license to a work.

If a work cannot be licensed, it can still be published in the Health Study Hub by granting the NFDI4Health the rights to publish it. In this case, the parts of a study document that have been taken from works of third parties must be marked in an appropriate manner, for example, by referencing the source of information. Any further questions or concerns about licensing works can be directed to: helpdesk@nfdi4health.de.

2.5 Persistent identifier

Any publication of study descriptions (metadata) or study documents can be minted with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). A DOI is a persistent identifier used to cite and link any objects — physical, digital or abstract — and guarantee their persistent findability. As a precondition for DOI assignment, study documents as well as their metadata must be stored in the Health Study Hub.

Also, the person submitting a resource must be authorized to mint a DOI, which means that the agreement of all parties holding intellectual property rights is provided and all authors, or creators, of the resource are specified. It is important to note that a DOI will only be assigned if the study document that is being published is a first publication. If a study document has already been published before and has been minted with a DOI, it is not possible to assign a second DOI.

2.5.1 Identifiers and versioning of resources

Whenever an entry is first published in the Health Study Hub, it is assigned an identifier (ID)⁸. The identifier is the prefix “nfdi4health-” followed by a consecutive number and is added to any resource at the end of its Uniform Resource Locator (URL). For example, if an entry has ID: nfdi4health-1, its corresponding URL is: <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1>. In the event of adaptations or adjustments being made to an entry’s metadata subsequent to its publication, even when only typographical errors are being corrected, a new version of metadata is published. The initial version is then saved as version one while the new, adapted version is saved as version two.

The changes are also visible in the URLs: The “original” entry with URL <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1> is now given an additional /1.0 at the end, to indicate

⁸ The DOI refers to the description of the study (= metadata), not to the study itself.

that it is version one: <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1/1.0>. The version including the changes will have URL <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1/2.0>, to indicate version two. Since the URL always links to the most current version, version two (in this case) will also be displayed when the original link <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1> is visited.

In the future when a new version of an entry is published, the publication team will be able to decide whether the changes made to the entry qualify for a new minor version of the entry or a new major version. Minor versions will be chosen if the changes made are mainly typographical. The version will then change from <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1/1.0> to <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1/1.1>.

If the changes made to the entry provide new information, i.e. additional metadata fields have been filled in or the corresponding study document has been updated, a major version will be chosen.

The URL will change from <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1/1.0> to <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-1/2.0>, as pointed out in the example above. As per default, for the time being every adaptation made to an entry will lead to a new major version.

If the original entry had been assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the DOI will not be affected by these changes and a new DOI will not be minted. An exception to this is if a study document has been assigned a DOI and changes are made to this document, i.e. and a new document is uploaded. In the future, it will be for the authors to decide whether a new DOI should be assigned after these changes.

In making this decision, two factors should be considered: Firstly, the extent to which the revised document differs from the original document; and secondly, whether the changes affect the content of the document and provide new information. If the changes are mainly orthographic (similar to a new minor version), the document should not be assigned a new DOI. Should the authors opt to assign a new DOI to the revised document, the metadata should also be adapted to reflect the changes made. Figure 2 illustrates the different procedures in the Health Study Hub:

Figure 2. Assignment of Identifiers (IDs) and Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to different versions of (study) metadata and study document entries in the Health Study Hub.

In order to not generate too many versions of one metadata entry by updating it several times, it is advised that longitudinal cohort studies with different populations are registered as follows:

One metadata entry, resource type “Study”, for the baseline study

One metadata entry, resource type “Substudy”, per follow-up investigation,

as demonstrated in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Illustration of how to record longitudinal cohort studies in the Health Study Hub.

An example of this on the Health Study Hub is the Study of Health in Pomerania – START:

<https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/nfdi4health-156>

2.6 Study documents and file formats

To make study documents findable and interoperable, provided file formats should be open (non-proprietary), machine-readable and -actionable. Formats like **.xml**, **.txt**, **.csv**, **.json**, **PDF(A)** or **.rdf** are preferred.

Non-machine-readable formats like common PDF and proprietary formats like **.xlsx** or **docx** are accepted. However, this will reduce the interoperability and reusability of the study documents. Below is a table of publishable study documents along with definitions and – where applicable – recommended file formats⁹:

Table 1: List of publishable study documents and their corresponding definitions and file formats

Study document	Definition
Study protocol (study plan, study proposal)	Formal plan of an experiment or research activity, including the objective, rationale, design, materials and methods for the conduct of the study; intervention description, and method of data analysis. [NCI, https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/concept/ncit/C70817 Recommended format: .pdf
Data dictionary (data catalogue)	Provides detailed descriptions of variables in a dataset. It typically includes information such as variable names, descriptions, data types, units of measurement, and any codes or categories used. It is primarily used to describe the structure and content of variables in a dataset. <i>NB: Data dictionary and Code book (listed below) are often used interchangeably. Some software tools provide data dictionaries (according to the above definition) but use the term ‘codebook’ for them.</i> [NLMN, https://www.nlm.gov/guides/data-glossary/data-dictionary Recommended format: CDISC ODM, .csv
Dataset	A collection of structured data in a single file, it lists values for each of the variables for each member of the dataset.

⁹ Publishable study documents as defined in the NFDI4Health Metadata schema V3_3, <https://art-decor.org/ad/#/nfdhtfcov19-/project/publication>

	<p><i>NB: This only applies to non-personal datasets, explained on p.4 of this document.</i></p> <p>[NCI, https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/concept/ncit/C47824, NFDI4Health]</p> <p>Recommended format: CDISC define.xml, .SQL, .json, .csv, .xls</p>
Participant/Patient information sheet	<p>(1) A document that informs the patient about procedures, potential risks or side effects of a proposed medication or operation.</p> <p>(2) A document that informs the patient about data being collected.</p> <p>[NFDI4Health]</p> <p>Recommended format: open, .mp4, .mpeg, .mpg, .mov, .avi</p>
Participant tasks	<p>A description of tasks that participants are asked to carry out as a part of the data collection process. For example, marking places on a map, taking photographs, telling a fairy tale, etc.</p> <p>[DDI, https://rdf-vocabulary.ddialliance.org/ddi-cv/TypeOfInstrument/1.1.2/TypeOfInstrument.html]</p> <p>Recommended format: .txt, .doc, .pdf</p>
Informed consent form (template)	<p>A process by which a participant or their legally accepted representative voluntarily confirms their willingness to participate in a trial after having been informed and been provided with the opportunity to discuss all aspects of the trial that are relevant to the participant's decision to participate. Varied approaches to the provision of information and the discussion about the trial can be used. This can include, for example, providing text in different formats, images and videos and using telephone or video conferencing with investigator site staff. Informed consent is documented by means of a written or electronic, signed and dated informed consent form. Obtaining consent remotely may be considered when appropriate.</p> <p>[ICH E6(R3) Guideline, https://database.ich.org/sites/default/files/ICH_E6%28R3%29_DraftGuideline_2023_0519.pdf]</p> <p>Recommended format: .txt, .doc, .pdf, FHIR, web form</p>
Manual of operations/standard operating procedures (SOPs)	<p>Written instructions for doing a specific task/operation in a certain way. In clinical trials, SOPs are set up to store records, collect data, screen and enrol subjects, and submit Institutional Review Board (IRB) applications and renewals.</p> <p>[NCI, https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/concept/ncit/C48443]</p> <p>Recommended format: .pdf</p>

<p>Data management plan</p>	<p>Describes the types of data researchers intend to collect or generate during their research process. It also states how the data will be used and stored during their lifecycle. A DMP serves to answer questions such as the following: description of the research project, type of data involved, how the data will be organised, data usage, metadata and referenceability, storage and security, publication, legal aspects and anonymization, (long-term) digital preservation. [Publisso, https://www.publisso.de/en/research-data-management/rdm-planning/, NFDI4Health] Recommended format: .pdf</p>
<p>Statistical analysis plan</p>	<p>A document that contains a more technical and detailed elaboration of the principal features of the analysis described in the study protocol, and includes detailed procedures for executing the statistical analysis of the primary and secondary variables and other data. [NCI, https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/concept/ncit/C115761] Recommended format: .pdf</p>
<p>Questionnaire</p>	<p>Set of predetermined questions or items shown to a study participant in order to get answers for research purposes. Some common question types include single choice, multiple choice, Likert scale, and open questions. [NCI, https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/concept/ncit/C17048, NFDI4Health] Recommended format: CDISC ODM, FHIR questionnaire, .pdf</p>
<p>Case report form (CRF)</p>	<p>Designed to record all of the clinical study-required information stipulated in the protocol to be reported to the sponsor on each clinical trial subject [NCI, https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/concept/ncit/C40988] Recommended format: CDISC ODM, FHIR questionnaire, .pdf</p>
<p>Code book</p>	<p>As a mode of secondary data collection, content coding applies coding techniques to transform qualitative data (textual, video, audio or still-image) originally produced for other purposes into quantitative data (expressed in unit-by-variable matrices) in accordance with pre-defined categorization schemes. <i>NB: Code book and Data dictionary (listed above) are often used interchangeably. Some software tools provide data dictionaries (corresponding definition above) but use the term 'codebook' for them.</i></p>

	<p>[DDI, https://rdf-vocabulary.ddialliance.org/ddi-cv/ModeOfCollection/4.0.3/ModeOfCollection.html, NFDI4Health] Recommended format: CDISC ODM, .csv</p>
Interview schema and themes	<p>Set of partly predetermined questions asked to a study participant in order to get answers for research purposes. Differs from a questionnaire in that the answers are not written down by a participant but given verbally to the interviewer. Questions are usually more open than in a questionnaire and answer options are less likely to be given. [NFDI4Health] Recommended format: .txt, .doc, .pdf</p>
Observation guide	<p>Guidelines regarding what will be observed. Depending on the study design, an observation guide can be more or less structured, ranging from exact specifications and scales to loosely formulated ideas. [DDI, https://rdf-vocabulary.ddialliance.org/ddi-cv/TypeOfInstrument/1.1.2/TypeOfInstrument.html] Recommended format: .txt, .doc, .pdf</p>
Discussion guide	<p>Guidelines for a group discussion. Depending on the study design, a discussion guide can be more or less structured, ranging from exactly formulated questions to general ideas on what to discuss. For example, a list of topics to be discussed in a focus group, or themes formulated by a researcher to direct a blog discussion, etc. [DDI, https://rdf-vocabulary.ddialliance.org/ddi-cv/TypeOfInstrument/1.1.2/TypeOfInstrument.html] Recommended format: .txt, .doc, .pdf</p>
Biobank	<p>A repository that collects, catalogues, and stores samples of biological material, such as urine, blood, tissue, cells, DNA, RNA, and protein, from humans, for laboratory research. Along with the samples, medical information may also be stored along with a written consent to use the samples in laboratory studies. [NCI, https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/concept/ncit/C48800] Recommended format: N/A</p>
Secondary data source	<p>Data that are collected from someone other than the primary user/researcher. Sources for secondary data can include census, information collected by</p>

	<p>government departments (e.g., social security, tax records), and data that were originally collected for other research purposes.</p> <p>[SAGE Encyclopedia, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304794138_Secondary_Data_sources_advantages_and_disadvantages]</p> <p>Recommended format: depends on the type of resource</p>
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2.7 Quality Assessment of the uploaded study/registry metadata and study documents

After metadata has been entered into the entry mask and the corresponding study documents have been uploaded to the Health Study Hub, the entries will undergo a formal quality assessment by the publication team before they are released. This is necessary to ensure that the entries comply with the NFDI4Health's quality standard as well as the FAIR data principles. To make sure that entries will pass the quality assessment, the following information should be considered:

- Even though not all fields are mandatory, it is advised to fill in **as many fields as possible**.
On top of the mandatory fields, the following fields should be filled in to ensure the findability of an entry:
 - Language of the resource
 - Keywords describing the resource
 - If applicable: Web page of the resource
 - Affiliation name
 - Email address or phone number
 - Affiliation Address (Street name, street number, post code, city, country (all separated by commas))
 - Web page of the affiliation
 - Affiliation Identifier: ROR ID
 - If applicable: related resources, such as journal articles or study documents

If the resource is a study/substudy/registry, the following **additional fields** should also be filled in:

- Primary purpose of the Study
- Type(s) of data sources
- Applied sampling method
- Eligible gender
- Inclusion/exclusion criteria

- If applicable: Obtained sample size
 - If applicable: Additional fields on dietary assessments
 - If applicable: Additional fields on chronic diseases
-
- If the title and/or description are provided in two languages, e.g. English and German, they ought to be **equally informative**, i.e., one should be the full translation of the other.
 - Titles should be informative. A dataset should have a **telling name** and should not be named “Raw data S1”.
 - The Health Study Hub does not have a built-in spell checker. **The spelling** of metadata should be checked before submitting any entries.
 - It is advised **to check all links**, e.g. keywords, web pages, ROR IDs, and DOIs of journal articles, to make sure that they work.
 - If **inclusion / exclusion criteria** are provided, they should be listed as follows:
 - criterion1; - criterion 2; - criterion3.A hyphen before each criterion and a semicolon after each criterion except for the last.
 - At least one **contributor** must be stated. For this information to be useful, apart from the name/affiliation, a full postal address as well as a website and email or phone number should be given. Just stating a name/affiliation is not going to be as useful for interested researchers that find a resource. A list of all eligible contributor types along with their definitions can be found in the DataCite Metadata Kernel¹⁰, pp40. Contact or sponsor(primary) are used most frequently.

Listing **related resources** is useful to a) link study documents that are registered on the Health Study Hub to a study b) link publications like journal articles to the study. A list of all eligible relations between a study and study documents along with their definitions can be found in the DataCite Metadata Kernel¹¹, pp 58. Generally, “is described by” is used for journal articles on studies whereas “is part of” is used for study documents used within the study.

The publication team will check all entries along the above-mentioned requirements. Should an entry not meet all of them, an e-mail will be sent to the author of the entry. This email will list which requirements are not met yet and what adjustments should be made before the entry can be published. By making sure that an entry meets all requirements before it is submitted, the duration of the quality assessment can be shortened, and the entry will be published sooner.

¹⁰ DataCite Metadata Kernel, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v4.4.pdf

¹¹ DataCite Metadata Kernel, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v4.4.pdf

3. Contact information

Should there be any questions and/or concerns about the publication of resources in the Health Study Hub or if additional support is needed, the research data publication team will gladly be of assistance: helpdesk@nfdi4health.de.

4. Acknowledgement

This work was done as part of the NFDI4Health Task Force COVID-19 and NFDI4Health Consortium (www.nfdi4health.de). The NFDI4Health gratefully acknowledges the financial support of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – project numbers 451265285 and 442326535.

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